

Additional Information

This document contains complementary information to the article “Test Generation from Use Case Specifications for IoT Systems: Custom, LLM-Based, and Hybrid Approaches”. You can find additional details concerning our IoT Use Case Specification Format, Test Case Format, Custom Approach (CA), evaluation methodology, results analysis and observations.

The approaches’ code is available upon request.

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Use Case Specification Format

In all our test case generation approaches, we used a Use Case Specification (UCS) format tailored to the needs and specificities of IoT Systems, ensuring all necessary information is included and presented in a formal, precise, and unambiguous manner, facilitating the use case analysis and information extraction process.

This format possesses all the information found in widespread Use Case Specification methodologies and frameworks like UML and RUCM, including the use case's name, description, basic flow and alternative flows (composed of steps), preconditions, postconditions, etc. Our IoT UCS format differs with its JSON-based structure and additional fields.

We chose to represent the use case in JSON due to its intelligibility, making it easily understood by both humans and systems, as well as its widespread support. This simplifies the UCS processing and analysis.

The addition of new fields is driven by the need for complete and exhaustive formally documented data, ensuring the quality and reliability of the information while guaranteeing that all necessary data is available to produce coherent and accurate test cases. These additions also directly address the specific needs and unique characteristics of IoT systems.

The additional fields are as follows:

- "primaryComponent" and "components" at the root level of the JSON UCS:
 - The "components" field lists all the IoT Nodes that comprise the system.
 - The "primaryComponent" field identifies the central Node of the system and the starting point of the generated test cases.
- "method", "protocol", "operation", "component", and "inputs" for steps with an input role: An input role refers to any communication between IoT Nodes, including data requests and data transmissions.
 - "protocol": Specifies the communication protocol used, such as HTTP, WebSocket, MQTT, etc.
 - "method": Indicates the protocol method used in the communication, such as POST (HTTP), send (WebSocket), or PUBLISH (MQTT).
 - "operation": Provides the formal name of the operation to be executed.
 - "component": Specifies the target device or subsystem that receives the data or request.
 - "inputs": A JSON array of strings that lists the names of all data being sent. These names are used as keys of the data sent in the "inputs" fields of the generated test cases.

- "outputs" for steps with an output role: An output role refers to responses to inputs, including any confirmation of actions or data sent as a reaction to the inputs.
 - "outputs": A JSON array of strings containing the expected response values.
- "condition" in alternative flows:

§ The "condition" field specifies the data condition for alternative branching, where applicable. This condition is represented as a JSON Schema property, which defines the data rules and constraints. The JSON Schema property syntax was chosen for its ease of use and specification, and widespread adoption.

Here's an example of a basic IoT UCS. For simplicity, some steps and alternative flows have been removed to better highlight the format:

```
{
  "useCaseName": "Normal heartrate.",
  "briefDescription": "WIMP use case when the heartrate is normal.",
  "precondition": [
    "BuddyApp is running.",
    "FitbitApp is running",
    "Connections have been initialized"
  ],
  "primaryActor": "WIMP",
  "secondaryActors": [],
  "primaryComponent": "WIMP",
  "components": [
    "Fitbit",
    "Buddy",
    "WIMP"
  ],
  "dependency": [],
  "generalization": null,
  "basicFlow": {
    "steps": [
      {
        "content": "The WIMP receives heartrate data from Fitbit",
        "method": "POST",
        "protocol": "HTTP",
        "operation": "Send fitbit data",
        "component": "WIMP",
        "inputs": [
          "data"
        ]
      },
      {
        "content": "The WIMP validates that heartrate is between 50 and 100 bpm" ,
        {
          "content": "The WIMP sends SPEAK command to Buddy with Normal message",
          "outputs": [
            "\"msg\": \"Normal\""
          ]
        }
      ]
    ],
    "postcondition": "The WIMP sent \"Normal\" message to Buddy."
  },
  "alternativeFlows": [
    {
      "type": "specific",
      "referenceFlowSteps": [2],
      "condition": "\"Data\": { \"type\": \"number\", \"not\": { \"minimum\": 50, \"maximum\": 100 }}",
      "steps": [
        {
          "content": "IF heartrate data is below 50 OR above 100 bpm THEN",
          {
            "content": "WIMP sends SPEAK command to Buddy with Special attention is Needed message",
            "outputs": [

```

```

        "msg": "Special Attention is needed"
    },
    { "content": "ABORT." }
  ],
  "postcondition": [
    "The WIMP sent \"Special Attention is needed\" message to Buddy."
  ]
}
]
}

```

While our UCS format is more in tune with the needs of IoT Systems, it remains subject to certain limitations. Despite specifying protocols, methods, and components, it does not currently support branching scenarios based on these elements. This limitation also applies to data types. In other words, the current documentation format of the use case does not support all potential branching conditions or situations, as there is no means to indicate incorrect or alternate protocols, methods, operations, target components, or data types. We acknowledge these limitations and intend to address them in future works.

Test Cases Format

The test cases generated by the approaches are represented as what we refer to as executable test payloads. These payloads are formatted in JSON and consist of three main fields: **TC_ID** (a unique identifier for the test case), **name**, and **steps**. A test case is essentially composed of multiple test steps which are found in the JSON array of the **steps** field. Each step corresponds to the execution of an operation and can be seen as a phase or stage of the test. It is an association between inputs and outputs (as specified in the UCS) to represent the complete communication and execution flow of the operation.

Each step includes the following fields:

- **"operation"**: Contains the formal name of the operation to execute.
- **"target"**: Includes essential information about the target node:
 - **"protocol"**: The communication protocol.
 - **"method"**: The method of the communication protocol to be used.
 - **"name"**: The target node or component (sub-system, device, etc.).
- **"inputs"**: Consists of the data sent to the target node.
- **"expectations"**: Represents the expected response or confirmation to the action taken.

Here's an example of a simple test case:

```

{
  "TC_ID": "TC001",
  "name": "Heartrate Check",
  "steps": [
    {

```

```

    "operation": "getFitbitData",
    "target": {
      "protocol": "HTTP",
      "method": "POST",
      "name": "Fitbit"
    },
    "inputs": {
      "data": bpm
    },
    "expectations": {
      "msg": "SUCCESS"
    }
  }
]
}

```

As you can see, the information in the test case is closely aligned with the formally documented data in the UCS. This alignment makes the test case generation process primarily consists of data pairing and reorganization.

Custom Approach (CA)

The custom approach is composed of 5 main steps: Use Case Extraction, Use Case Test Model Generation, Scenarios Extraction, Node Pairing and Test Generation.

Use Case Extraction

Like its name indicates, the first step of the CA is the extraction of the use case from its JSON format. Its file is read, and steps from all execution flows are classified into types: INPUT (IoT communication), CONDITION (branch start), OUTPUT (response), STEP (internal action), ABORT (premature end), and EXIT (normal end). Classification is based on step position, content, fields, and branching.

Use Case Test Model Generation

A Use Case Test Model (UCTM)} is a logic tree representing the use case, enabling its easy traversal and analysis. This step of the approach is simply the creation of such a model from the extracted use case. Each flow step is converted into a Node, and branching relationships between nodes are defined as a list of strings contained in the parent node.

Most nodes only have a single child, and in such cases, possesses only a single empty list. However, CONDITION Nodes have multiple lists, each containing all the relevant constraints (as JSON Schema properties) that define input data rules. To maintain accurate and

coherent constraint application across all branches, constraints to other branches are inverted using the JSON Schema “not” clause, ensuring only one condition is true at a time.

Let’s illustrate this with an example. If we have a Node of type CONDITION which has three children, one belonging to the basic flow and the other two coming from different alternative flows. The data branching condition for the first alternative flow, which we’ll call “A”, is “data”: { “type”: “number”, “maximum”: 50 } (any numeral value below 50) and the condition for the other alternative flow, which we’ll call “B”, is “data”: { “type”: “number”, “minimum”: 100 } (any numeral value above 100).

- The list for the relationship to stay in the basic flow will contain:
 - “data”: { “type”: “number”, “not”: { “maximum”: 50 } }
 - “data”: { “type”: “number”, “not”: { “minimum”: 100 } }.
- The list for the alternative flow A will contain:
 - “data”: { “type”: “number”, “maximum”: 50 }
 - “data”: { “type”: “number”, “not”: { “minimum”: 100 } }.
- The list for the alternative flow B will contain:
 - “data”: { “type”: “number”, “not”: { “maximum”: 50 } }
 - “data”: { “type”: “number”, “minimum”: 100 }.

This example is represented by the following figure:

Scenarios Extraction

When the UTCM is completed, the approach proceeds to extract the scenarios. A recursive implementation of a depth-first search (DFS) algorithm parses the UTCM, exploring all branches to create a scenario for each unique execution path, extracting and regrouping Nodes and their relevant data constraints.

Node Pairing

For each scenario extracted, multiple key nodes are paired together to form multiple associations that will later translate into test steps. Input nodes are paired with condition and output nodes. Each input node defines the protocol, method, target component, operation and identifies the data to send (its JSON key / its name). Condition nodes specify data constraints by combining the conditions from their relationship list into a comprehensive JSON Schema. This is achieved using "allOf" clauses combined with a predefined JSON Schema skeleton. External steps detail the test expectations.

Test Generation

In the final step of the Custom Approach, information is extracted from the paired nodes to create test case steps. Valid input values are generated using the [JSON Schema Faker library](#) with the constructed JSON Schema. The test case steps are then combined to form the complete test flow. Test IDs are assigned incrementally, and test names are derived from post-conditions.

Evaluation Methodology

To evaluate the performance of the four approaches we implemented, we used three use cases from the WIMP (Where Is My Professor) IoT system. We adapted them to our IoT UCS format, and we manually created expected test cases and defined acceptable data values which would serve as references.

Each adapted use case was provided to the implementations of all four approaches to generate test cases. The generated results were then compared to the references and evaluated on three level:

1. **Scenario coverage (Scenario Evaluation):** We evaluated the accuracy and coverage of the generated scenarios with the number of correctly and incorrectly

identified scenarios. The coverage, precision, and recall metrics were calculated for each use case, and an average was obtained for each approach.

2. **Correctness of generated tests (Step Evaluation):** Using only the scenarios correctly identified by each approach, we evaluated the presence and general correctness of each test case step in the scenarios. For a step to be considered valid it must represent the correct operation or test phase overall, it does not require all fields to be entirely accurate (which is covered by the next level). Coverage, valid proportion, precision, and recall were obtained for the steps of scenarios of each use case, with an overall average calculated for each approach.
3. **Correctness of each step (Fields Evaluation):** For the correctly identified steps, we assessed the correctness of their fields. We calculated the proportion of correctly generated fields for each use case and obtained their average results across all three use cases for each approach.

These three levels can be understood as levels of precision and granularity. **Scenario coverage** evaluates whether the generation process identifies all the correct scenarios, **correctness of the generated tests** determines if the tests are composed of the appropriate steps or phases, and **correctness of each step** assesses in detail the accuracy for the fields composing the steps.

The results can be found in the paper or [here](#).

Discussion

Results Analysis

The results show that, unlike the exclusively LLM-based approaches, both the custom and hybrid methods were flawless in identifying scenarios and steps. This is because they share the same mechanism for scenario identification and classification of use case steps, which in turn, also facilitates the pairing of scenario steps into test case steps. However, the hybrid approach outperformed the CA in terms of field correctness, making it functionally the best approach overall according to our results. This aligns with our earlier hypothesis that the hybrid approach would provide the best overall utilisation experience.

Surprisingly, the custom approach, which we previously noted should theoretically achieve perfect accuracy if the use case is flawless, encountered errors concerning the values of the input fields. Upon investigation, we determined that this issue is likely related to limitations of the JSON Schema Faker library, which struggles with handling complex JSON schemas. Specifically, the library has difficulty processing schemas that include incremented "not" and "allOf" clauses, which are essential to our custom approach.

The Single-Stage and Multi-Stage LLM approaches both struggled with identifying payload steps, but in different ways. The Single-Stage approach had low coverage and recall but achieved good precision. The Multi-Stage approach, on the other hand, demonstrated perfect coverage and recall but had lower precision.

The struggles of the Single-Stage approach could be seen as "lazy" behavior, as it often ignores the initial steps of scenarios and includes only the last one. This was predominately common for the last few scenarios it sent, where the first few steps were already identified in the basic flow. This could be explained by an assumption made by the model that it could skip over steps it already covered. It could also happen because the Single-Stage approach executes the entire process in a single step and response, potentially inciting the model to minimize the length of its output.

The Multi-Stage approach encountered the opposite issue. It had the tendency to split steps in two, assigning the expectations to a separate, made-up step that does not exist. This hallucination also explains the lower precision of the approach and its reduced accuracy for the expectation fields (outcomes), as the correct expectations were misplaced in the invented steps.

One aspect where LLM based approaches seemed to perform well was input data generation. The results show that both Single-Stage and Multi-Stage LLM approaches were perfect in generating test input, with the hybrid approach also having decent results. This can potentially be explained by the capacity of LLMs to analyze and understand the text, giving them more indications on values and their context. The slightly lower accuracy of the hybrid approach could potentially be explained by a difficulty to understand the complex Json schemas received from the previous step to represent data constraints for the accepted values.

Observations

When evaluating the approaches, we made several observations regarding their behavior and tendencies. While they may not directly impact the results, they may illustrate and reveal the characteristics and qualities of each approach. Since the custom approach was developed with our own algorithms and code, there were few surprises or notable observations to be made. For this reason, this sub-section primarily addresses behaviors of the LLM-based approaches.

Incomplete use cases specifications may cause problems with our IoT use case specification format because it ties data constraints to alternative flows as branching conditions. If no alternative flow exists for a specific data value, all values are considered valid due to the absence of formally defined constraints. This limitation was considered when manually creating the expected test cases used as a reference for evaluation. However, we observed that the LLM-based approaches often exceeded expectations by generating realistic values

for incomplete or not formally declared constraints. The LLMs analyzed the context and extracted information from the text to provide plausible values, which was not the case for the custom approach. This behavior supports our hypothesis that LLM-based approaches are more adaptable and flexible, performing better with incomplete use cases because of their ability to extrapolate, interpret context and text.

Another observation going in this direction was made when we made a mistake in the use case specification, causing the formal conditions to contradict part of the text. Despite this, the LLM-based approaches prioritized the textual description and produced realistic inputs. While this adaptability can be beneficial in such scenarios, it could also play against it in situations where the text is ambiguous or inconsistent.

One drawback we observed with the LLMs was their tendency to include code comments in the generated test cases, particularly when creating input data. These comments make the outputs invalid as JSON. This problem can be addressed easily by improving the prompts.

Potential Improvements

The current implementations of the approaches are currently basic and can be improved significantly to exploit their potential and increase their reliability. To do so, we consider the followings:

- **Prompt Optimization:** Continue to experiment with prompts and use prompt engineering techniques to find the optimal prompts for the LLM-based approaches.
- **Granularity Optimization:** Experiment to find the best step granularity for the LLM steps in the Multi-Stage and Hybrid approaches.
- **Task repartition:** Find the optimal task repartition between LLM and our algorithms in the hybrid approach.
- **LLM Fine-Tuning:** Fine-tune models to enhance their performance for their respective task.
- Experiment with multiple LLM models to find which one performs the best.

Other improvements will also need to be done to the IoT Use Case format and our approaches to solve their current limitations.